

Synthesis, spectral characterization and DNA-binding properties of dinuclear copper(II) complexes of 2,2'-bipyridyl containing bridging mono anionic ligands

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Abstract : The mononuclear Cu^{II} complex, [Cu(bpy)(NO₃)₂] (**1**) obtained by the reaction of 2,2'-bipyridyl (bpy) with Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O in methanol solution, reacts with mono anionic ligands, bromide, iodide and thiocyanate in MeOH solution to form stable binuclear complexes [Cu₂(bpy)(μ-X)(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₂, where X = Br⁻ (**2**), I⁻ (**3**), SCN⁻ (**4**). These complexes were characterized based on electronic, IR, ESR, magnetic moments and conductivity measurements. The electrochemical behaviour of the complexes was investigated by cyclic voltammetry. The interactions of these complexes with calf thymus DNA were investigated using absorption spectrophotometry. Electronic absorption data suggest that the complexes bind DNA via intercalation.

Keywords : Synthesis, dinuclear copper complexes, bipyridyl, spectral studies, DNA binding.

Introduction

Design and synthesis of molecules, mimicking natural enzyme, have important applications in the development of new therapeutics¹. DNA has become an interesting target for artificial enzymes, partly because of possible therapeutic applications². In past two decades, a variety of transition metal complexes have been used in developing artificial nucleases by either hydrolytic or oxidative pathway, with or without sequence specificity³⁻⁵. Currently, there are more and more frequent examples of catalytic systems based on two metal ions reported in chemistry and in biochemistry, because many enzymes that catalyze phosphate ester cleavage are activated by two or more metal ions⁶⁻⁸. Copper complexes have been extensively investigated in this application since they possess biologically accessible reductive potentials and high affinity with nucleic acids⁹⁻¹¹. Thus inorganic chemists are fascinated to investigate copper complexes which are capable of cleaving DNA catalytically.

Heterocyclic bases can effectively complex many transition metal ions which might then alter their binding properties to nucleic acids and thus be useful as a spectroscopic probe and could also act as chemical nucleases¹². These ligand systems, in combination with some bridging groups may be able to hold two or more metal centers,

mimicking the multinuclear metal arrays at the active sites of several metallo-enzymes^{12,13}. Synthesis and characterization of mononuclear copper(II) complex (bpy)Cu(NO₃)₂ and its reactivity towards hydroxide and azide anions to form binuclear complexes are reported in the literature¹⁴.

In the light of the above, and as a part of our ongoing research programme¹⁵⁻¹⁸ concerning DNA-binding and cleavage activities of dinuclear transition metal complexes, herein we report the synthesis, spectral characterization and DNA binding properties of new dinuclear copper(II) complexes containing bridged mono anionic ligands.

Results and discussion

The reaction of Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O with an equimolar amount of bpy in methanol results in the formation of a blue complex **1**. It reacts with anionic ligands, Br⁻, I⁻ and SCN⁻ in methanol to form the stable binuclear complexes [Cu₂(bpy)X(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₂, where X = Br⁻ (**2**), I⁻ (**3**) and SCN⁻ (**4**). The complexes are obtained in good yields. The complexes are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic. Therefore, the complexes may be stored very easily. The complexes are partially soluble in water, methanol, ethanol and readily soluble in acetonitrile (CH₃CN), DMF and DMSO. Our several attempts to obtain diffraction quality crystal for the complexes using different com-

bination of solvents were not successful. The magnetic moments of complexes **1**, **2**, **3** and **4** are 1.09, 0.74, 1.10 and 0.87 B.M. respectively. The magnetic moments of the dinuclear complexes (**2-4**) less than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) suggesting the presence of magnetically coupled metal centers in these complexes¹⁹. The molar conductivity data suggest that complex **1** ($8 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) is a non-electrolyte whilst complexes **2-4** (89, 91 and $110 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively) are 1 : 2 electrolytes²⁰. Physicochemical and analytical data of complexes are given in Table 1.

cm^{-1} region²². N-bonded complexes exhibit a single sharp $\nu(\text{NCS})$ band near 480 cm^{-1} , whereas S-bonded complexes show several peaks²³ near 421 cm^{-1} . Complex **5** shows two strong bands, at 2090 and 2115 cm^{-1} , indicating that this complex has sulphur coordinated as well as $-\text{S}(\text{CN})-$ bridging ligand. A band at 775 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{CS})$ of bridged $-\text{SCN}-$. A strong band is observed at 1384 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of complexes indicating the presence free nitrate ion. Molar conductivity data suggest that the complexes (**2-4**) are 1 : 2 electrolytes. Hence the complexes **2-4** have nitrate counter anions in analogy with our

Table 1. Physico-chemical and analytical properties of copper(II) complexes

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	Melting point (°C)	Molecular weight Found (Calcd.) %	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen	Metal
1.	[Cu(bipy)(H ₂ O)(NO ₃) ₂]	Blue	256–258	360 (361.5)	33.65 (33.19)	2.70 (2.76)	15.40 (15.51)	17.63 (17.57)
2.	[Cu(bipy)(H ₂ O) ₂ Br] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Brown	246–248	796 (794.88)	29.50 (30.19)	2.95 (3.02)	10.20 (10.56)	16.15 (15.98)
3.	[Cu(bipy)(H ₂ O) ₂] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Brown	222–224	910 (908.88)	26.10 (26.40)	2.62 (2.64)	9.30 (9.24)	14.05 (13.98)
4.	[Cu(bipy)(H ₂ O) ₂ SCN] ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	Green	220–222	750 (751.08)	33.25 (33.55)	3.25 (3.19)	13.10 (13.05)	17.50 (16.92)

LC-MS mass spectra are added in support of binuclear structure of complexes. In mass spectra of complexes **2**, **3**, and **4**, peaks are observed at (m/z) 796.9 (794.8), 909.3 (908.8) and 751.8 (751.1) corresponding molecular ion peaks. LC-MS figures are given in Supplementary files. The calculated values are given in parenthesis.

IR spectra :

The IR spectrum of complex **1** shows strong absorptions at 1383 and 1275 cm^{-1} , in a region typical for $\nu(\text{NO})$ of coordinated nitrates²¹. Complex **1** also exhibits a strong band at 3443 cm^{-1} assigned to $-\text{OH}$ stretching of a water ligand. In the IR spectra of complexes **2**, **3** and **4** similar bands were observed at 3443 , 3443 and 3434 cm^{-1} , respectively, also suggesting the presence of a water ligands. The SCN group may coordinate to a metal through the nitrogen, sulphur, or both sulphur and nitrogen. The CN stretching frequencies are generally lower in N-bonded complexes (near and below 2050 cm^{-1}) than in S-bonded complexes (near 2100 cm^{-1}) and bridging $[\text{M}-\text{SCN}-\text{M}]$ complexes exhibit $\nu(\text{CN})$ well above 2100 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{CS})$ bands for S-bonded complexes are found in the 720 – 690

previous observation¹⁵.

Electronic spectra :

The copper(II) complexes exhibit two strong bands in the 37037 – 38167 cm^{-1} region, assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the bpy ring. The peak appeared (27027 – 32051 cm^{-1}) in the spectra complexes is assigned to a charge transfer transition (LMCT). A weak band observed in 14326 – 15526 cm^{-1} region is assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ electronic (d-d) transition in favour of octahedral structure²³.

ESR spectra :

ESR spectra of copper complexes were recorded at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT) in both solution (DMF) and solid state. Typical ESR spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Cl})]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in powder state at 300 K , at liquid nitrogen temperature, in DMF solution at 300 K and at liquid nitrogen temperature are shown in Fig. 1. The spin Hamiltonian and orbital reduction parameters of copper complexes are given in Table 2. The g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are computed from the spectrum using tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) free radical as 'g' marker. It is significant from the data that the observed g_{\parallel} values for

Fig. 1. X-band powder ESR spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complex : (A) at 300 K, (B) at LNT, (C) in DMF solution at 300 K and (D) DMF solution at LNT.

all these copper complexes are less than 2.3 suggesting covalent character of the metal-ligand bonding²⁴. In the solid state, similar spectra of these complexes at 77 K and 300 K indicates that the geometry around copper(II) ion is unaffected on cooling to liquid nitrogen temperature. In these conditions the axial symmetry parameter G , which measures the interaction between copper centres in unit cell is calculated from the following equation²⁵.

$$G = [g_{\parallel} - 2.0023/g_{\perp} - 2.0023]$$

The calculated G values are found to be less than 4 for the copper complexes suggesting that there is considerable interaction between two copper ions in the solid complex²⁶. The broad ESR spectra clearly reveal that there is strong antiferromagnetic interaction between two metal ions in the complexes. This antiferromagnetic coupling occurs due to the quenching of the spin of electrons of one metal ion by the adjacent metal ion²⁷.

ESR spectra were recorded in DMF at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature to obtain more accurate molecular values by giving four hyperfine signals for all the complexes. The ESR parameters (g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp}) of the complexes and the energies of d-d transitions are used²⁸⁻³¹ to evaluate spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) and the orbital reduction parameters (K_{\parallel} , K_{\perp}). The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.0023) observed for these complexes suggests that

Table 2. The Hamiltonian and orbital reduction parameters of copper(II) complexes

Sl. No.	Complex	In solid state				In liquid state				α^2					
		g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	G	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	G		λ	K_{\parallel}	K_{\perp}	$A_{\parallel} \times 10^{-5}$	$A_{\perp} \times 10^{-5}$
1.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	2.15	2.08	2.10	1.84	2.23	2.06	2.12	3.86	444	1.93	0.51	0.124	0.0013	0.88
2.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Br}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.20	2.08	2.12	2.49	2.14	2.07	2.10	1.87	362	1.48	0.75	0.0038	0.0018	0.32
3.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{I}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.12	2.07	2.09	1.61	2.17	2.10	2.12	1.69	648	0.98	0.55	0.0057	0.0015	0.41
4.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{SCN}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	2.17	2.07	2.10	2.47	2.21	2.06	2.11	3.16	610	1.80	0.56	0.0094	0.0031	1.40

the unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital³² of the copper(II) ion. For all the complexes the lowest g value greater than 2.0023 is also consistent with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state. The spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) value is calculated using the relation,

$$g_{av} = (g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp})^{1/3} \text{ and } g_{av} = 2(1 - 2\lambda/10Dq),$$

is less than the free copper(II) (832 cm^{-1}) which also supports covalent character of M-L bond.

Based on molar conductance, magnetic moment, electronic, FT-IR and LC-MS spectral data a general structure (Fig. 2) is assigned to copper(II) complexes having bridging monoanionic ligands.

Fig. 2. A general structure of dinuclear complex.

Electrochemical behavior :

The redox behaviour of the complexes has been investigated by cyclic voltammetry in DMF using 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate as supporting electrolyte. Table 3 gives the electrochemical data obtained at the glassy carbon electrode in DMF. The cathodic peak current function values were found to be independent of the scan rate. The cyclic voltammograms obtained from repeated scans as well as various scan rates are very similar. The CV profiles suggest that dissociation of complex does not occur in DMF medium. A typical cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{I}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complex at different scan rates is shown Fig. 3. The difference between cathodic and anodic peaks (ΔE_p) in-

creases with increasing scan rate. This observation suggests quasi-reversible behavior of complexes. Quasi-reversible nature reduction is evident from (i) non equivalent current intensity³³ cathodic and anodic peaks and from (ii) the difference $\Delta E_p = E_{pc} - E_{pa}$. The ΔE_p in all these complexes exceeds the Nernstian requirement $59/n \text{ mV}$ (n = number of electrons involved in the redox process) which suggests quasi-reversible character. All these complexes have large separation (76–349 mV) between the anodic and cathodic peaks, indicating the quasi-reversible character. $\log K$ values and ΔG values suggest that the complexes are stable in DMF medium.

Electronic absorption titrations :

The binding interactions of the complexes with CT-DNA were monitored by comparing their absorption spectra with and without CT-DNA. Fig. 4 shows absorption spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Br}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complex in the presence of increasing amounts of DNA. In the presence of increasing amounts of DNA, the spectra of all complexes showed a strong decrease (hypochromicity) in intensity with shift in absorption maxima towards higher (bathochromic shift) wavelengths. The extent of hypochromism and red shift is commonly consistent with the strength of intercalative interaction^{34,35}.

The binding constants (Table 4) suggest that the complexes bind DNA very strongly. On addition of DNA, the absorbance of the complexes decreases (hypochromism) and absorption maximum of all complexes is shifted to higher wavelength (bathochromism). These observations suggest that the complexes bind DNA through partial intercalation of planar bipyridine moiety.

Conclusions

The dinuclear copper(II) complexes having bridging monoanionic ligands are characterized based on analytical and spectral (electronic, IR, ESR and LC-MS) data.

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric data of copper(II) complexes

Sl. No.	Complex	Redox couple	C_V cathodic E_{pc}	C_V anodic E_{pa}	ΔE_p (mv)	$E_{1/2}$	i_c/i_a	$\log K_C^a$	$-\Delta G^b$
1.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	II/I	-0.089	0.261	349	0.086	1.405	0.096	552
2.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Br}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	II/I	0.183	0.512	329	0.347	1.823	0.102	585
3.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{I}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	II/I	0.085	0.536	329	0.310	0.817	0.074	425
4.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{SCN}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	II/I	0.148	0.461	313	0.304	0.490	0.107	614

^a $\log K_C = 0.434 ZF/RT\Delta E_p$; ^b $\Delta G^0 = -2.303 RT \log K_C$.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram profile of $[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{I}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ at different scan rates.

that the complexes bind DNA through intercalation. Electrostatic attraction between the cationic complex and the negatively charged phosphodiester backbone of DNA may also contribute to the binding constant^{36,37}.

Experimental

Analytical grade 2,2'-bipyridyl (bpy), $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, KCl, KBr, KI, and KSCN were obtained from Merck. The solvents used for synthesis of the metal complexes were distilled before use. Calf thymus DNA (CT-DNA) was purchased from Genie Bio labs, Bangalore, India. Equipment used in the characterization of complexes are described before¹⁸.

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Br}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in the absence and in the presence of increasing concentration of CT-DNA; top most spectrum is recorded in the absence of DNA; a plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ versus $[\text{DNA}]$ is shown in the inset.

Table 4. Electronic absorption data upon addition of CT-DNA to the complex

Sl. No.	Complex	λ_{max} (nm)		$\Delta\lambda$ (nm)	H%	K_b (M^{-1})
		Free	Bound			
1.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	312	313	1	+1.96	3.92×10^6
2.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Br}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	306	307	1	+46.85	5.71×10^6
3.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{I}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	310	311	1	+3.90	1.39×10^6
4.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{SCN}]_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	311	310	1	+19.40	1.87×10^6

The data (K_b) obtained in electronic absorption titrations suggest that the complexes bind DNA strongly. The spectral changes of complexes upon addition of DNA suggest

Preparation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (1) :

The complex was prepared by following the procedure given in literature¹⁴. To a stirring solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

3H₂O (1.21 g, 5 mmol) in MeOH (10 mL), a solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl (0.78 g, 5 mmol) in MeOH (10 mL) was added slowly. The stirring was continued for 30 min. The blue complex was filtered off and washed with a small quantity of MeOH. Yield : 1.27 g.

Preparation of [Cu(bpy)(H₂O)₂(Br)]₂(NO₃)₂ (2), [Cu(bpy)(H₂O)₂I]₂(NO₃)₂ (3) and [Cu(bpy)₂(SCN)]₂(NO₃)₂ (4) :

To a stirring solution of complex (1) (0.77 g, 2 mmol) in MeOH (20 mL), excess KBr/KI/KSCN was added, and stirring was continued for 1 h. On slow evaporation of reaction solution, the coloured complex was formed. It was filtered off and washed with a small quantity of MeOH and dried in vacuum.

DNA-binding experiments :

Interaction of the complexes with CT-DNA was studied by electronic absorption spectroscopy. The experimental procedures are described before¹⁸.

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